

TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY DRESDEN

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

The basis for policies on gender-based violence (GBV) at German universities is the General Equal Treatment Act (AGG) issued in 2006. It defines forms of discrimination, explicitly including sexual harassment, and obliges higher education institutions (HEIs) to establish a complaints unit for any discrimination-related issues. However, the AGG only includes employees, not students. In addition to national legislation, HEIs have to comply with regional laws and can create their own regulations. At present, there are over 400 HEIs in Germany, and there are no systematic data available on how many have developed regulations on GBV (Kocher & Porsche 2015). According to a survey conducted among HEIs, 54% of participating HEIs had established a complaints unit for cases of discrimination according to the AGG by 2016 (Antidiskriminierungsstelle des Bundes 2020).

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

The process of creating a policy on GBV started quite recently at TU Dresden. One policy specifically dedicated to GBV has been produced to date: the Guideline on Dealing with Harassment, Discrimination, and Violence. The Guideline on Dealing with Harassment, Discrimination, and Violence was developed under the lead of the GE Commissioner during a two-and-a-half-year participatory process involving different stakeholders at the institution, including students. Before that, there were almost no resources, contact points, information, or monitoring activities relating to GBV.

The policy document is divided into nine parts that describe: the scope of the policy, definitions, prevention, counselling and support for affected persons, the Complaints Office at TU Dresden, the complaints procedure, sanctions, data security, quality assurance, and entry into force. The document applies to all members and associate members of the university and describes two ways of dealing with incidents: counselling and support provided by different contact points (including gender equality officers, designated representatives of people with disabilities, non-Germans, employees, etc.) and filing an official complaint with the Complaints Office (as designated by the Rectorate). In addition, it discusses different forms of prevention measures, but in a general and non-binding way.

The main responsible stakeholders are the Gender Equality Commissioner and the contact person at the Complaints Office.

URLs

- › Guideline on Dealing with Harassment, Discrimination, and Violence:
<https://tu-dresden.de/tu-dresden/organisation/ressourcen/dateien/Gleichstellungsbeauftragte/Unsere-Themen/gleichstellungsdokumente/richtlinie-sdg-eng?lang=en>

Entry into force: 2019.

TRAINING

The Gender Equality Commissioners and the contact person at the Complaints Office have been trained to deal with situations of GBV. A further essential component of preventive work is an effective information policy, which ensures that existing offers and contact persons are known to all members of TU Dresden and their families. 'To inform' also entails developing and implementing further regular training events on prejudiced structures and corresponding intervention approaches and the professionalisation of existing counselling centres.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

Not specified in the institutional fieldwork report.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: The policy addresses the following **four** forms of GBV: sexual violence, sexual harassment, gender-based harassment, and stalking.

- Gender-Based Violence
- Physical Violence
- Psychological Violence
- Sexual Violence
- Sexual Harassment
- Gender-Based Harassment
- Economic and Financial Violence
- Stalking
- Organisational Violence
- Online Violence
- Other

7Ps covered: The policy addresses all **7Ps**: prevalence, prevention, protection, prosecution, provision of services, partnership and policy.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Target groups

Academic staff
 Non-academic staff
 Students
 Other

Intersectionality addressed

No.

Specific vulnerable groups

None.

The policy addresses all target groups and identifies other groups. In scope the policy applies to all members and associate members of TU Dresden.

Bystanders addressed: No.

Role of perpetrators addressed: No.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: No.

Monitoring: Yes. The Complaints Office reports regularly to the Department of Human Resources, the Pro-rectorate of University Culture, and the Staff Council.

Evaluation: Yes. The policy must be evaluated two years after its introduction, which in this case means the evaluation took place in the fall of 2021.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

The policy sets out a single step-by-step procedure for all, for reporting and investigation.

The policy defines: who to contact, how to report, responsible persons/units, outcomes, and sanctions.

Who to contact / How to report: '6.1 All persons defined under Point 1 of these Guidelines have the right to complain to the Complaints Office of Technische Universität Dresden (according to point 5).

6.2 The complaint can be made by post, e-mail, or in person.

6.3 The complaint should describe the events. Any witnesses and/or evidence available should be named. It should also be stated whether and to what extent other persons have already been informed about the incidents and whether and to what extent measures have already been taken.

6.4 Plaintiffs shall be made aware of support measures and counselling services and shall be subject to an appropriate and transparent procedure. The complaint shall be examined and the plaintiff notified of the outcome.'

Responsible persons/units: Complaints Office

Outcomes / sanctions: '6.5 If, as a result of the incidents described above, labour/disciplinary measures are considered (see point 7), the Complaints Office's Personnel Department must become involved immediately. In the event that measures against students need to be considered (see also point 7), the Complaints Office must immediately involve the offices responsible for implementing sanctions against students.'

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

Acknowledgment: *this vignette has been created on the basis of the work carried out by national researchers Monica Perez and Friederike Kressner in 2021, as part of the deliverable report D5.1 Inventory of policies and measures to respond to GBV in European universities and research organisations (2022). Available here: https://zenodo.org/record/5939082#.YfvXE_jTW5c*

